

References

1. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 947.
2. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1241.
3. S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and G. PATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.

Methanolysis of the Anhydride of 1-Carboxycyclohexane-1-Acetic Acid : A Comment.

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Manuscript received 11 October 1977, accepted 25 January 1978

IN contradiction to the earlier reports by Khuda and Bhattacharya¹, who depicted the formation of the half-ester-acid (III) by methanolysis of the anhydride (I), Saharia and his co-workers² have recently reported that methanolysis of the anhydride (I) produces the isomeric half-ester-acid (II) as the only product.

- (II) R=CH₃; R'=H
 (III) R=H; R'=CH₃
 (IV) R=R'=C₂H₅
 (V) R=C₂H₅; R'=H
 (VI) R=R'=CH₃

In connection with synthetic studies in resin acids it was reported from this laboratory³ that partial hydrolysis of the diethyl ester (IV) gives the mono acid ester (V). Accordingly, partial hydrolysis (5% methanolic potassium hydroxide—1 hr) of the dimethyl ester (VI), [n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.51 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.50 (br s, 2H methylene), 3.60 (s, 3H, -CH₂-COOCH₃) and 3.65 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)] prepared from the corresponding diacid^{4,5} by esterification with an excess of ethereal diazomethane, produces the half-acid ester (II) as the major acidic product, m.p. 56° [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H, methylene), 2.55 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOH), 3.65 (s, 3H, t-COOCH₃) and 10.00 (br s, 1H, COOH, exchangeable with D₂O)]. In the present study the methanolysis of anhydride (I) according to Saharia and his co-workers² afforded a mixture of two half-acid esters (II) and (III) containing Ca 10-15% of (II) as estimated from the integration ratio of the respective methyl ester singlets in the ¹H n.m.r. spectrum. After repeated column chromatography on silica gel using petroleum ether—ether (9:1), eluents furnished the pure half acid ester (III) [¹H n.m.r. δ (CCl₄) 1.50 (br s, 10H methylene), 2.53 (br s, 2H, -CH₂-COOCH₃), 3.60 (s, 3H, -COOCH₃)

and 10.80 (s, 1H, —C—COOH, exchangeable with D₂O)] as a thick liquid. The present reinvestigation

thus confirms again the general observations⁶ recorded for the opening of substituted succinic anhydrides by treatment with alcohols.

The author thanks Prof. U. R. Ghatak for his suggestion to undertake this problem, which was brought to his notice by Dr. P. C. Bhattacharya, Department of Chemistry, Vidyasagar College, Calcutta.

References

1. M. QUDRAT-I-KHUDA and K. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 15.
2. H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI, R. K. GAUTAM and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1076.
3. U. R. GHATAK, N. N. SAHA and P. C. DUTTA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 79, 4487.
4. E. RO'YTHSTEIN and J. F. THORPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2011.
5. A. LAPWORTH and J. A. M. RAE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2741.
6. M. S. NEWMAN, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1956, p. 228; N. N. SAHA, B. K. GANGULY and P. C. DUTTA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 3670.

Chemical Investigation on *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don.

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Manuscript received 20 January 1977, revised 18 October 1977,
accepted 6 December 1977

THE neutral fraction of the benzene extract of the fern *Polypodium juglandifolium* Don on careful chromatography afforded two hydrocarbons together with six alcohols shown in Table 1.

Fernene, flicene, cyclolaudenol and dryocrassol were identified by direct comparison with authentic specimens (m.m.p and Co-IR). The mother liquor from the crystallisation of cyclolaudenol was seen to be a mixture of two compounds one of which was cyclolaudenol (TLC). The mixture of alcohols (A), m.p. 121-22°, on acetylation gave an acetate (B), m.p. 107-108°, (α)_D + 55.17° and on catalytic hydrogenation in presence of Pd-C gave a compound (C), m.p. 132-34°, which on acetylation gave an acetate (D), m.p. 127-28°. NMR spectra of the original mixture (A) and its acetate (B)

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM *P. Juglandifolium*

Sl. no.	Compound (Str. no)	M. p. (°C)	$[\alpha]_D$	Mol. formula
1.	Fernene ¹	169–70	–16.3°	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
2.	Filicene ¹	231–32	+49.6°	C ₃₀ H ₅₀
3.	Cyclolaudenol ¹ (Ia)	122–23	+45°	C ₃₁ H ₅₂ O
4.	Cycloneolitsol(Ib)	176–80	–	C ₃₂ H ₅₄ O
5.	Polypodinol A ² (IIa)	223–25	–89.13°	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O
6.	Polypodinol B ² (IVa)	165–66	+28.57°	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O
7.	Dryocrassol ⁴	245–47	+65°	C ₃₀ H ₅₂ O
8.	Polypodinol C(IVd)	149–51	–3.28°	C ₃₀ H ₅₀ O

both showed distinct peaks at δ 4.65 (-CH₂) and 4.68 (-3H, -CH₂, -CH OAc) respectively but in the corresponding spectrum of (C) the peak due to vinylidene group was absent indicating that both the compounds in the mixture contained a -CH₂ group. Oxidation of the mixture (A) with Jones reagent gave a mixture of ketones (E), m.p. 117-18°. Mass spectra of (A), its acetate (B), the dihydro-compound (C) and its acetate (D) indicated that along with cyclolaudenol (M⁺ 440) a second component (M⁺ 454), that is, a new C-32 triterpene alcohol C₃₂H₅₄O was present in the mixture (A). The mass spectral fragmentation shown in Table 2 when examined with the fragmentation pattern of cyclolaudenol Ia^{5,6,7} clearly indicated that the new compound was closely related to cyclolaudenol having an extra carbon (-CH₂) in the side chain¹. The position of the double bond (-CH₂, NMR) in the side chain may be tentatively assigned from the mass spectrum of (A) as the M-84 fragment observed in the McLafferty rearrangement involving the 24, 28 double bond^{5,8} and the C(20) hydrogen has been found to be absent.

From the foregoing evidence, two probable structures Ib^{9,10} and Ic can be assigned to the new C-32 compound. After extensive PLC of the mixture of alcohols (A) cyclolaudenol (Ia) and 5 mg of cycloneolitsol (Ib)⁹⁻¹², m.p. 176-80°, could be isolated. The acetate of the latter, m.p. 165-67°, was found to be identical with a sample of cycloneolitsol acetate.

TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRAL FRAGMENTS OF COMPOUNDS (m/e VALUES)

Compound	M	M - 15	M - 18	M - 18 - 15	Other fragments				
			OR M - HOAc	OR M - HOAc - 15					
(A)	440	425	422	407	300	379	175	315	
	454	439	436	421	314	393			
(B)	482	467	422	407	300	379	175	357	297
	496	481	436	421	314	393			
(C)	442	427	424	409	302	381	175	315	
	456	441	438	423	316	395			
(D)	484	469	424	409	302	381	175	357	297
	498	483	438	423	316	395			

Polypodinol A (Table 1) ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 3605 (OH), gave the acetate IIb, m.p. 203-204°, (α)_D-83.72°, ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 1725, 1245; NMR (CDCl₃) of IIa δ 0.8-1.28 (8 *t*-CH₃), 5.40 (*m*, trisubst. double bond) and 4.40 (-CH-OH) and IIb δ 0.8-1.18 (8 *t*-CH₃), 2.0 (3H, -O.CO.CH₃), 5.40 (*m*, 1H, vinyl proton), 5.20 (1H, CH-OAc) suggested it to be a secondary alcohol in a triterpenoid skeleton. IIa & IIb did not show any UV absorption in the region 200-300 nm. CrO₃-Py oxidation of IIa gave a ketone IIc C₃₀H₄₈O (M⁺424), m.p. 221-23°, (α)_D+16.06°, ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 1720. Wolff-Kishner reduction of IIc gave fernene, m.p. 168-69°, (α)_D-16.6° (identical with an authentic sample) indicating that IIa is a hydroxy derivative of fernene. MS of IIa *m/e* 426, 339, 271, 257 strongly suggested that (OH) group is present in ring A or B. C.D. curve of the ketone IIc showed a strong positive Cotton effect $\Delta\epsilon$ 3.39 at 296 nm. Inspection of the Dreiding model suggest that the C-6 ketone would adopt a twist conformation with a positive Cotton effect but a C-7 ketone ($\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated) would most probably give rise to a negative Cotton effect¹³. This is further confirmed by CMR Spectrometry. In the spectrum of fern-9 (11)-ene, a signal at 52.1 ppm is assigned to C-5 and that at 59.7 ppm to C-8 (estimated 50 and 55 ppm respectively by comparison with model compounds A₁-D₁). If 13 ppm is added for the effect of an α -carbonyl¹⁴, the predicted values are in good agreement with the observed ones (Table 3).

TABLE 3—CMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF IIc AND IVc

Compound	Predicted (with models A ₁ , B ₁ , C ₁ , D ₁)	Predicted (with fernene as model)	Found
6-keto (IIc)	CH(C ₆)65	65.1	63.4
	CH(C ₈)52	59.7	54.5
	CH ₂ (C ₇)44	—	42.6
7-keto (IVc)	CH(C ₆)67	72.7	70.9
	CH(C ₈)49	52.1	47.1
	CH ₂ (C ₄)36	—	35.0

Dehydration of IIa with POCl₃-Py afforded a single product III (TLC), m.p. 157-58°, no UV absorption in the region 220-300 nm, NMR (CDCl₃): δ 5.28 (*m*) and 5.44 (*m*) [two vinyl protons], indicating β -axial orientation of the (OH) group at C-6. NaBH₄ reduction of the ketone IIc gave the epimeric (6 α -OH) compound IVd, m.p. 200-201°, acetate m.p. 177-79°. Oxidation gave back the original ketone.

Polypodinol B (Table 1) ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 3590 (OH), NMR (CDCl₃): δ 0.8-1.25 (8 *t*-CH₃), 5.40 (*m*, 1H, vinyl proton), 4.26 (-CH-OH), gave a monoacetate IVb, m.p. 207-208°, (α)_D+38°, NMR (CDCl₃): δ 0.8-1.16 (8 *t*-CH₃), 2.08 (3H, -O.CO.CH₃), 5.16 (*m*, CH₂-CHOAC). IVa showed no UV absorption between 220-300 nm. CrO₃-Py oxidation gave a ketone IVc, C₃₀H₄₈O (M⁺ 424), m.p. 174-75°, ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 1720

(6-membered ring ketone), NMR (CDCl₃): δ 0.8-1.04 (8 *t*-CH₃), 5.38 (1H, vinyl proton). Wolff-Kishner reduction of IVc gave fernene identical with an authentic sample. IVc was different from 3-keto fern 9(11)-ene. C.D. curve of the ketone showed a strong negative Cotton effect. Examination of the Dreiding models with C-15 and C-16 ketone in the fernene nucleus separately suggests that the compound with C-15 ketone would have a very small Cotton effect probably positive, whereas the compound with C-16 carbonyl group would show a strong positive Cotton effect. Since a negative Cotton effect was observed, we believe that the carbonyl group is probably situated a C-7 as in IVc and polypodinol B is IVa. CMR of the ketone IVc (Table 3) also indicates the assigned structure.

Polypodinol C (Table 1) ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 3430 (OH), NMR (CDCl₃) δ 0.8-1.2 (8 *t*-CH₃), 5.35 (1H, vinyl H), 4.4 (CH₂-CH-OH), gave a monoacetate IVe, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺ 468), m.p. 193-95° (α)_D+30°, ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 1720, 1245 (O.CO.CH₃), no UV absorption between 220-300 nm. CrO₃-Py oxidation of IVd gave a ketone, m.p. 168-70°, ν_{max}^{nujol} cm^{-1} 1725. Wolff-Kishner reduction of the ketone gave fernene indicating that IVd is a hydroxy derivative of fernene. C. D. spectrum of the ketone shows a strong negative Cotton effect for the carbonyl group, $\Delta\epsilon$ -7.58 at 301 nm in methanol solution. The ketone m.p. 168-70° was found to be identical with 7-keto fernene IVc in all respects (m.m.p, IR, NMR, CMR), showing thereby that the polypodinol C was an epimer of polypodinol B. When IVc was reduced with sodium borohydride in methanol, it afforded an alcohol m.p. 151-52° identical with polypodinol C. Thus, polypodinol-C (IVd) is most probably the equatorial isomer and polypodinol B (IVa) is the axial isomer.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. B. C. Das, CNRS, Gif-Sur-Yvette for the mass spectra, Dr. P. M. Scopes, Westfield College, London for C. D. curves, Prof. G. Ourisson, Laboratoire-Associé au CNRS, Institut-de-Chimie, Strasbourg, France, for an authentic specimen of cycloneolisol acetate and Prof. H. Ageta, Showa College of Pharmaceutical Science, Tokyo, Japan for IR comparison of dryocrassol and its acetate.

References

1. D. R. MISRA and H. N. KHASTGIR, Abstract, Proc. Indian Sci. Cong. (59th) Assoc., Chemistry Section, p. 137, Calcutta, 1972, Abstract, Convention of Chemist, p. 8, Madurai, 1974.
2. D. R. MISRA and H. N. KHASTGIR, Abstract, Convention of Chemist, p. 87, Allahabad, 1972.
3. D. R. MISRA, T. K. RAY and H. N. KHASTGIR, Abstract, Proc. Indian Sci. Congr. (61st) Assoc., Chemistry Section p. 99, Nagpur, 1974.
4. H. AGETA, K. SHIOJIMA, Y. ARAI, T. KASAMA and K. KAJI, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1975, 3297.
5. R. T. APLIN and G. M. HORNBY, *J. Chem. Soc. (B)*, 1966, 1078.
6. B. BENVENISTE, L. HIRTH and G. OURISSON, *Phyto Chemistry*, 1966, 5, 31.

7. H. E. AUDIER, R. BENGLMANS and B. C. DAS, *Tetrahedron letters*, 1966, 4341.
8. J. BERGMAN, B. O. LINDGREN and C. M. SVAHN, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1965, 19, 1661.
9. E. RITCHIE, R. G. SENIOR and W. C. TAYLOR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 2371.
10. R. LABRIOLA and G. OURISSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, 27, 1901.
11. Y. TACHI, S. TAGA, Y. KAMANO and M. KOMATSU, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. (Japan)*, 1971, 19, 2193.
12. R. SUNDER, K. N. N. AYENGER and S. RANGASWAMI, *J. Chem. Soc. (Perkin-I)*, 1976, 117.
13. P. CRABBE, "Optical rotatory dispersion and Circular Dichroism in Organic Chemistry", Holden-Day, Sanfrancisco 1965, p. 232 and references cited therein.
14. "Topics in Carbon-13 NMR Spectroscopy", Vol. 2 p. 92-105, 1976, Wiley-Interscience, edited by George Levy.

Synthesis of New Schiff's Bases : Terephthalaldehyde Bis (Semicarbazone) and Terephthalaldehyde Bis (4-Phenylthiosemicarbazone)

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Manuscript received 17 August 1977, accepted 6 December 1977

THE present communication is in continuation with the work¹⁻³ on coordination polymers in progress in these laboratories and describes the synthesis of bidentate coordinating ligands obtained by the condensation of terephthalaldehyde with semicarbazide or 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. The reactions are :

(I)

(II)

The composition of compounds TPBS (I) and TPBPTS (II) have been established from elemental analyses data, and the structures elucidated through a study of infrared spectra (table 1).

TABLE 1—INFRA-RED SPECTRA (CM⁻¹) OF TEREPHTHALALDEHYDE BIS (SEMICARBAZONE) AND TEREPHTHALALDEHYDE BIS (4-PHENYLTHIOSEMICARBAZONE)

TPBS	TPBPTS	Band assignments
3540s 3320m	3480m 3340w	N-H stretching
3020w 3000s	3040m	=C-H stretching
2320m	2330m	-C=N absorption of Schiff's base
1685s	1680vs	C=N stretching
1660s	...	C=O stretching
1645s 1640sh	1645s 1640sh	NH ₂ deformation
1590vs 1540s 1500s	1590vs 1550s 1500s	C=C and C=N-N stretching vibrations
1495s 1440vs ...	1480s 1430s 1340vs	C=S and N-C-N stretching C-N stretching of the Ar-N type
1155s 1070vs	1140s 1080s	para-di substituted phenyl ring
920vs 830s 730vs	975s 870s 750vs	C-H out of plane bending vibrations
495vs	450s	N-C-N deformation

s = strong, vs = very sharp, sh = shoulder, w = weak, m = medium

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